

ASSESSING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE TECHNICAL-VOCATIONAL-LIVELIHOOD EDUCATION IN TERMS OF IMPLEMENTATION AND LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study is to assess the effectiveness of the TVL Curriculum in terms of its extent of implementation and learning environment among 160 TVL students of Valencia City, Bukidnon, specifically in Valencia National High School, STI College – Valencia, and Paramount School of Arts, Languages, Management, and Sciences, Incorporated. This research utilized descriptive research design and descriptive statistics for the statistical analysis. The study's results in terms of the implementation of the TVL curriculum scored 4.09, which means moderately observed. It signifies that the students are satisfied with the availability of enhancement programs, equipment and facilities, references, and a conducive learning environment. The dimensions of the learning environment also scored 4.27, meaning that the students highly observed the facilities and resources, teaching and learning arrangements, and practical training periods. It concludes that implementing the TVL curriculum in Valencia City, Bukidnon, is compelling in terms of its extent and learning environment. This research recommends frequent assessment in the different areas of the TVL curriculum to ensure that it remains significant and aligned with the purposes and needs of society. Enhancement of facilities, constant monitoring of the learning objectives, competency, and skill enhancement for

the TVL teachers are all necessary factors that must be maintained to succeed in the implementation of the TVL curriculum.

Keywords: *Learning Environment, TVL Curriculum, Satisfaction, Facilities, Skill Enhancement*

INTRODUCTION

The Technical Vocational and Livelihood (TVL) track aims to develop job-ready competencies in its students. It translates to equipping them with the foundational knowledge, practical skills, and professional dispositions necessary for effective career performance and long-term success in the labor market. This skills-based pathway empowers students to transition directly into the workforce upon graduation or pursue further skill development and educational opportunities (Garra & Baes, 2023). The K-12 program envisions graduates as global assets with 21st-century skills and ethical values to thrive in an interconnected world. The TVL track fosters workforce-ready skills combined with innovative thinking and strong moral character (Department of Education, 2016).

Resource scarcity, particularly a need for more equipment, facilities, and materials, poses a significant obstacle to successfully implementing the TVL track in the Philippines. This is especially evident in agri-fishery arts, where the absence of dedicated farming areas impedes the development of essential practical skills. Similar resource constraints plague other TVL strands, further hindering students' ability to acquire industry-relevant skills. It echoes a global concern, where inadequately educated workforces remain a significant impediment to business competitiveness despite skilled human resources' crucial role in national development. Addressing these resource limitations is essential to ensure the TVL program delivers its intended outcome of empowering students with job-ready skills and contributing to a globally competitive workforce (Geraldizo & Dabazol, 2022).

A report evaluating the implementation of the Senior High School (SHS) program paints a concerning picture for the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) track. The study pinpoints several significant roadblocks, including deficiencies in curriculum delivery and work immersion, students' lack of prior preparation, partnering challenges, shortages of qualified instructors, and inadequate material resources. These combined factors raise concerns about the track's ability to effectively equip students with job-ready skills, highlighting the need for urgent interventions to address these critical issues and ensure the program's success (Ramos, 2021).

In this study, assessing the TVL curriculum guarantees students gain valuable skills in a practical setting. By measuring the extent of its implementation, it tracks individual progress and job readiness while evaluating the learning environment, ensuring classrooms and teaching methods align with real-world needs, aiming to optimize student

development and career preparation. It focuses on the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood Track students of Valencia City, Bukidnon, Philippines.

Research Questions

This study investigated the effectiveness of the TVL Curriculum in terms of its implementation and learning environment. Specifically, the researchers sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the extent of implementation of the TVL curriculum?
 2. What is the learning environment under the TVL curriculum in terms of:
 - a. Facility and Resources;
 - b. Teaching and Learning Experiences at the School and;
 - c. Practical Training Period?
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METHODOLOGY

This quantitative research utilized a descriptive method to assess the implementation and learning environment of the TVL Curriculum. The 160 respondents of this study were taken from the TVL students of Valencia National High School, STI College of Valencia, and Paramount School of Arts, Languages, Management, and Sciences, Incorporated. The research instrument used is the questionnaire of Geraldizo & Dabazol (2022) used in their study entitled Assessment of the Senior High School Technical-Vocational Livelihood Track adapted from Quality in VET-schools of Leonardo De Vinci Education and Culture. SPSS is utilized to perform the descriptive statistics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Analysis on the Extent of Implementation of the TVL Curriculum

Assessing the extent of implementation of the TVL curriculum is crucial for its ongoing effectiveness and relevance in preparing students for successful careers. This commitment to continuous improvement ultimately leads to a more successful program for the students and a valuable contribution to the workforce and economy.

Table 1: Extend of Implementation indicators of the TVL Curriculum

INDICATORS	MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE RATING	QUALITATIVE INTERPRETATION
School-based skills enhancement program helps students get a National Certificate (NC I, II, III).	4.26	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
Opportunities to get guidance for some learning difficulties are accessible.	4.19	Agree	Moderately Observed
Sufficient books and references are available anytime.	4.18	Agree	Moderately Observed
Similar core and applied subjects help senior high school students who want to transfer to another area of specialization.	4.11	Agree	Moderately Observed
The classroom benefits learning (internal and external premises are clean).	4.06	Agree	Moderately Observed
Enough machines, tools, and other equipment are required for learners' skills enhancement.	4.04	Agree	Moderately Observed
There are sufficient facilities for the learners, like television, projector, portable speaker, and other facilities for classroom instructions.	4.01	Agree	Moderately Observed
The school offers a bridging program for students who want to transfer to another strand.	3.85	Agree	Moderately Observed
OVERALL	4.09	Agree	Moderately Observed

Legend:

Scale	Interval	Description	Qualitative Interpretation
5	4.21- 5.00	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
4	3.41- 4.20	Agree	Moderately Observed
3	2.61- 3.40	Undecided	Fairly Observed
2	1.81- 2.60	Disagree	Seldom Observed
1	1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree	Not Observed

Table 1 shows the growth points of the TVL curriculum. It reveals the overall mean score of 4.09 (agree), which means moderately observed in the following indicators namely: "School-based skills enhancement program helps students get a National Certificate (NC I, II, III);" (4.26); "Opportunity to get guidance for some learning difficulties is accessible," (4.19); "Sufficient books and references are available anytime," (4.18); "Similar core and applied subjects offering help senior high school students who want to transfer to another area of specialization," (4.11); "Classroom is beneficial to learning (internal and external premises are clean)," (4.06); "There are enough machines, tools, and other equipment for learners' skills enhancement," (4.04); "There are sufficient facilities for the learners like television, projector, portable speaker, and other facilities for classroom instructions," (4.01); "Bridging program for students who want to transfer to another strand is offered in the school," (3.85). It implies that most students are satisfied with implementing the TVL curriculum, especially with the availability of enhancement programs, equipment and facilities, references, and a conducive learning environment.

In the study conducted by Ferrer (2022), the TVL track was well-implemented in terms of facilities, equipment, and learning environment. Despite its status, it still requires time-to-time response evaluation in implementing the curriculum to ensure quality assurance.

Tungol's study (2019) confirmed that the implementation of the TVL curriculum is perfect in terms of curriculum adjustment, national certificate passing rate, administration, and management.

Descriptive Analysis on the Learning Environment of the TVL Curriculum

Facilities and Resources

The table below shows the study arrangement of the students under the TVL curriculum. It reveals the overall score of 4.21 (strongly agree), which means moderately observed in the following indicators, namely: “Teaching aids are available as planned.”(4.30); “Institution’s facilities, tools, and equipment work properly” (4.25); “.Teaching aids are available as planned.” (4.25); “ Classroom arrangements are well-organized.”(4.21); “TVL workshops and laboratories are available in the school.”(4.20); “Opportunities to use the machines, tools, and IT (email and software) at the institution are wide open,”(4.19); “Learning competencies taught are aligned to TESDA’s needed skills.”(4.13); “Technical assistance in problems related to skill mastery or other information systems is available.”(4.12). This implies that study arrangement is highly conducive for students because the curriculum competencies are aligned with TESDA skills, technical assistance is always available, teaching aids are planned, and workshops and laboratories are also available. Overall, the TVL students have access to the needed facilities and competencies necessary for their training.

Table 2: Assessment of the TVL curriculum in terms of facility and resources

INDICATORS	MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE RATING	QUALITATIVE INTERPRETATION
Teaching aids are available as planned.	4.30	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
Institution’s facilities, tools and equipment work properly.	4.25	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
Students can use the equipment when need it.	4.25	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
TVL workshops and laboratories are available in the school.	4.20	Agree	Moderately Observed
Classroom arrangements are well-organized.	4.21	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
Opportunities to use the machines, tools, and IT (email and software) at the institution are wide open.	4.19	Agree	Moderately Observed
Learning competencies taught are aligned to TESDA’s needed skills.	4.13	Agree	Moderately Observed
Technical assistance in problems related to skill mastery or other information systems is available.	4.12	Agree	Moderately Observed
OVERALL	4.21	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed

Legend:

Scale	Interval	Description	Qualitative Interpretation
5	4.21- 5.00	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
4	3.41- 4.20	Agree	Moderately Observed
3	2.61- 3.40	Undecided	Fairly Observed
2	1.81- 2.60	Disagree	Seldom Observed
1	1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree	Not Observed

In the study by Barrera (2022), with proper arrangement of the curriculum necessities, such as teaching aids and competencies aligned to TESDA, the student's learning progression will be hindered. However, this challenge should motivate the curriculum to enhance and innovate the availability of instructional resources. In the study by Belandres & Dioso (2023), to assess the studying arrangement of the TVL curriculum, TVL teachers and administrators should evaluate their implementation using the Training Regulations of TESDA for the competency standards and other necessary materials for the program.

Teaching and Learning

Table 3: Assessment of the TVL curriculum in terms of teaching and learning process

INDICATORS	MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE RATING	QUALITATIVE INTERPRETATION
The learning objectives of the studies were explained to the students.	4.45	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
Opportunity to ask the teachers a feedback on updates of the trends and developments of courses offered is explained.	4.36	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
Learning objectives are achieved.	4.35	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
Various teaching methods have been used (pair work, group work).	4.35	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
Interests in learning across discipline have grown	4.31	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
Teachers' professional skills were up-to-date.	4.29	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
Teachers were competent in discussing the topic.	4.27	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
The assessment criteria for the studies were explained at the beginning of the school year	4.26	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
Group work sessions help improved the learning process.	4.26	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
Students' different backgrounds were taken into account in instruction.	4.26	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
The school provides opportunities to participate in national, regional, or division, based activities.	4.25	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
Students' assessment results are returned within a reasonable period of time.	4.21	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
Teaching groups are small enough for students' learning.	4.18	Agree	Moderately Observed
Students' capability to work in a national or international working environment has been improved.	4.18	Agree	Moderately Observed
Teachers assessed students equally.	4.14	Agree	Moderately Observed
OVERALL	4.27	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed

Legend:

Scale	Interval	Description	Qualitative Interpretation
5	4.21- 5.00	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
4	3.41- 4.20	Agree	Moderately Observed
3	2.61- 3.40	Undecided	Fairly Observed
2	1.81- 2.60	Disagree	Seldom Observed
1	1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree	Not Observed

Table 3 shows the teaching and learning setup in the TVL curriculum. The learning objectives of the studies were explained to the students”(4.45),”.Opportunity to ask the teachers feedback on updates of the trends and developments of courses offered is presented which in the following indicators namely,”(4.36); “Various teaching methods have been used (pair work, group work).,”(4.35); “Learning objectives are achieved.”(4.35); “Interests in learning across discipline have grown,;(4.31); “Teachers’ professional skills were up-to-date”(4.29); “Teachers were competent in discussing the topic.,”(4.27);” The assessment criteria for the studies were explained at the beginning of the school year.,”(4.26); “Group work sessions help improved the learning process.,”(4.26), “Students’ different backgrounds were taken into account in instruction.,”(4.26),. “Teaching groups are small enough for students’ learning.”(4.18); “Students’ capability to work in a national or international working environment has been improved.”(4.18); “Teachers assessed students equally.”(4.14);” On-time feed backing on the status in academics and practical performances are given.” (4.13). This implies a well-established teaching and learning relationship between teachers and students. The essential learning outcomes and competencies are delivered, and teachers’ skills are updated. The high passing rate for the national certificate assessments is evidence of the well-implemented TVL curriculum.

In the study of Pangan (2022), the students were delighted with the teaching and learning process in the TLE and TVL curricula. The results also revealed that the students were pleased with the teaching and learning quality, especially the skill training methods. These produced skilled students with National Certificates in their respective skill areas. Santos (2021) suggests that to improve further the teaching and learning process in the TVL track, strict compliance with the curriculum guide ensures that the materials and tools to be enhanced are aligned with the essential learning outcomes. Additionally, integrating real-life skills helps them develop their TVL skills and competencies.

Practical Training Period

The table below shows the practical training period in the TVL curriculum. It reveals the overall score of 4.33 (strongly agree), which is highly observed in the following indicators: “Orientation was conducted to explain the necessary safety and security issues at the workplace.”(4.43), “People at the workplace treated me appropriately.”(4.41); “Practical learning period helped the learners improve their learning achievement.”(4.39), “Practical learning promoted further employment opportunities.”(4.32); “Students received sufficient guidance at the workplace or during work immersion.”(4.28),. “Students were satisfied with the practical learning period or work immersion.,”(4.27); “Learners achieved the objectives or goals set for practical learning period or work immersion.,”(4.26); “Students knew what they were supposed to learn during work immersion.,”(4.26). This implies that the practical training period of the students is well-implemented, especially the work immersion period, practical learning period, and workplace orientation.

Table 4: Assessment of the TVL curriculum in terms of Practical Training Period

INDICATORS	MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE RATING	QUALITATIVE INTERPRETATION
Orientation was conducted to explain the necessary safety and security issues at workplace.	4.43	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
People at the workplace treated me appropriately.	4.41	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
Practical learning period helped the learners improve their learning achievement.	4.39	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
Practical learning promoted further employment opportunities.	4.32	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
Students received sufficient guidance at the workplace or during work immersion.	4.28	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
Students were satisfied with the practical learning period or work immersion.	4.27	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
Students knew what they were supposed to learn during work immersion.	4.26	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
Learners achieved the objectives or goals set for practical learning period or work immersion.	4.26	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
OVERALL	4.33	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed

Legend:

Scale	Interval	Description	Qualitative Interpretation
5	4.21- 5.00	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
4	3.41- 4.20	Agree	Moderately Observed
3	2.61- 3.40	Undecided	Fairly Observed
2	1.81- 2.60	Disagree	Seldom Observed
1	1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree	Not Observed

Kosimov (2015) suggests that an improved practical training period constitutes improving the students' professional skills and knowledge. It helps the students master the skills and abilities necessary for applying acquired knowledge in practice, planning production processes that characterize their profession, preparation, implementation, monitoring, and maintenance.

Summary of the Learning Environment in the TVL curriculum

Table 5: Summary of the Findings in Learning Environment

DIMENSIONS	MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE RATING	QUALITATIVE INTERPRETATION
Practical Training Period	4.33	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
Teaching and Learning	4.27	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
Studying Arrangement	4.21	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
OVERALL	4.27	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed

The table above summarizes the different dimensions of the learning environment in the TVL curriculum. The overall score is 4.27 (Strongly Agree), which means Highly Observed from the following dimensions, namely: "Practical Training Period" (4.33), "Teaching and

Learning” (4.27), and “Studying Arrangement” (4.21). This implies that the TVL students are satisfied with the curriculum setup and learning environment. It signifies that the students have proper facilities and competencies regarding skill enhancement and training.

The study of Alarcon, Dumagan, Lumakang, and Nuezca (2022) highlights the importance of the learning environment as a necessary component of student’s motivation and enjoyment. In their study, it shows that it has a significant influence on student’s learning. Additionally, if the students are comfortable with their environment, they explore more and show authentic learning. Vallesteros (2022) suggests improving the training environment so that students’ hands-on practical skills will also be improved.

Conclusions

Based on the results and findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

Assessment of the effectiveness of the TVL curriculum in the extent of implementation revealed that the student expresses contentment with the execution of the TVL curriculum, explicitly highlighting their satisfaction with the accessibility of enhancement programs, well-equipped facilities, abundant references, and a conducive learning environment. The learning environment of this curriculum in terms of facilities and resources, teaching and learning, and practical training period were highly observed by the TVL students. It signifies that the students have proper facilities and competencies regarding skill enhancement and training. Therefore, the TVL curriculum is effective based on its implementation and learning environment.

Recommendations

A multifaceted approach is crucial to enhance the TVL program. Curriculum revisions should emphasize industry-aligned skills and integrate innovative teaching methods. Work immersion needs stronger partnerships with industry leaders for realistic and impactful experiences. Student preparation can be improved by bridging the gap between primary and senior high education, while teacher training should focus on developing relevant technical skills and pedagogical expertise. Addressing resource scarcity requires increased government funding, creative resource sharing among institutions, and leveraging technology for virtual learning opportunities. Career guidance and entrepreneurial training can also empower graduates for diverse career paths. By implementing these changes, the TVL program can become a highly regarded effort for skill enhancement of individuals and propelling national economic growth.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research adhered to all relevant ethical standards and guidelines, including obtaining informed consent from participants, ensuring anonymity and confidentiality of data, and avoiding any practices that could cause harm or distress. Additionally, the research design was conducted transparent and unbiasedly, and the findings were presented accurately and objectively.

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